

Text Information retrieval with Term frequency matrix

CSCI 765 – Introduction to Database Systems

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December 2023

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1. Problem statement

Retrieving documents based on linear scan of a corpus for query terms is impractical and slow, particularly when dealing with a large volume of documents and increasing number of terms in a query. In addition, multiple terms in a query would require processing of different documents in the corpus and it is important to present query results by order of relevance.

This project aims to develop a pragmatic document retrieval system which accepts query input as a text and divulge relevant list of documents sorted by relevance, the most relevant documents being presented at the top. The implementation improves the response time for end-user web applications, where the requirement is to retrieve files under 2 seconds.

Documents are modelled using a bag of words technique, specifically the inverted index which is also known as term document matrix (TDM). The matrix is a vector space model which stores frequency of terms that appear in each document without considering semantics or grammar. When a user makes keyword-based queries the inverted index is used to generate a dictionary displaying document names matched with relevance scores in a sorted manner.

The implementation uses natural language tool kit¹ (NLTK), python's text processing library, for text pre-processing, Django framework for the implementation of the WebApp and PostgreSQL for storing the text files. Initially, text files were stored in MongoDB for the Django web app implementation, however due to MongoDB's poor integration with Django framework, PostgreSQL is used to store the text file even though it enforces strong structure and loses formatting of the text such as spaces and headlines. Despite not utilizing cutting-edge statistical algorithms, this implementation promises to be practical for retrieval of documents. The source code² and Jupyter notebook³ is available on GitHub.

¹ <https://www.nltk.org/>

² https://github.com/BeTKH/IR_postgres

³ https://github.com/BeTKH/ir_notebook/blob/main/IR_final.ipynb

2. Implementation steps

Figure 1 - Implementation steps of the information retrieval system

2.1 Setup and tools

A *pipenv* virtual environment is used for a comprehensive software package and dependency management. Text preprocessing and analysis is done with a Jupyter notebook using NLTK, Pandas, NumPy, and Plotly for visualization. A complete list of these packages and their versions is listed in the *pipfile*. The exact versions of the packages for deterministic build are stored in the *pipfile.lock* [1][2]. Visual Studio Code is used for editing and debugging the source code.

2.2 Data source

The project uses a text data - a collection of 18 text files that are downloaded from project Gutenberg using the Natural Language Processing Tool Kit (NLTK) library⁴. A list of English stop words is also downloaded from NLTK package for text processing steps later [3].

Once the text files are downloaded, each file is represented as list of tokens i.e. a unit of text that can be a single word or a character such as semi-colon or full stop.

```
import re
import os
import nltk
import collections
import numpy as np

def load_allfiles():
    # load all files from gutenberg
    file_names = nltk.corpus.gutenberg.fileids()

    return [nltk.corpus.gutenberg.words(file) for file in file_names]

# load data
filesList = load_allfiles()

print(len(filesList), "text documents\n")

file_names = nltk.corpus.gutenberg.fileids()
print("\nfile names are:", file_names)

18 text documents

file names are: ['austen-emma.txt', 'austen-persuasion.txt', 'austen-sense.txt', 'bible-kjv.txt', 'blake-poems.txt', 'bryant-stories.txt',
'burgess-busterbrown.txt', 'carroll-alice.txt', 'chesterton-ball.txt', 'chesterton-brown.txt', 'chesterton-thursday.txt', 'edgeworth-parent
s.txt', 'melville-moby_dick.txt', 'milton-paradise.txt', 'shakespeare-caesar.txt', 'shakespeare-hamlet.txt', 'shakespeare-macbeth.txt', 'wh
itman-leaves.txt']
```

⁴ <https://www.nltk.org/book/ch02.html>

2.3 Text Pre-processing

Text file cleaning is crucial since not all words within the files may be equally relevant for document retrieval. Standard text cleaning procedures involve case folding, elimination of special characters, removal of stop words, and stemming.

Case folding

Case folding refers to standardizing the letter case within words [4][5]. Achieving this uniformity can be accomplished with `casefold`, which is a built-in method for strings in python. An example of case folding a text is shown below:

```
def casefold_Text(text_):
    return [word.casefold() for word in text_]

# Test
testText = "This is a Test Text that has to be cleaned 155615 [ ] ROBERT ;) DROP TABLE Students;"

# casefolding
tokensList = testText.split()
cf_tokensList = casefold_Text(tokensList)

print("before casefolding:", testText)
print("after casefolding:", ' '.join(cf_tokensList))

before casefolding: This is a Test Text that has to be cleaned 155615 [ ] ROBERT ;) DROP TABLE Students;
after casefolding: this is a test text that has to be cleaned 155615 [ ] robert ;) drop table students;
```

Removing special characters

Special characters in a text like semicolons, asterisks, square brackets, etc., might be significant in certain text processing applications where semantics and grammar are important. However, for file retrieval application special characters are not particularly helpful and will be removed. Therefore, eliminating all special characters, including white spaces is necessary.

One way to remove special characters from texts is using regular expressions, also known as `regX`, with “`re`” - python’s built in module [6]. A regular *expression pattern*: `[a-zA-Z\s]` is used to remove special characters and numbers. A code snippet below shows the implementation.

```
# normalizing - remove special characters

# cleaning special characters
def normalize_Text(tokens):

    pattern = r"[^a-zA-Z\s]"
    clean_tokens = [re.sub(pattern, '', token) for token in tokens]
    clean_tokens = list(filter(None, clean_tokens))
    return clean_tokens

# Test text
testText = "This is a Test Text that has to be cleaned 155615 [ ] ROBERT ;) DROP TABLE Students;"

norm_testText = normalize_Text(testText.split())
print("before normalize_Text:", testText)
print("after normalize_Text:", ' '.join(norm_testText))

before normalize_Text: This is a Test Text that has to be cleaned 155615 [ ] ROBERT ;) DROP TABLE Students;
after normalize_Text: This is a Test Text that has to be cleaned ROBERT DROP TABLE Students
```

Removing stop-words

Stop words are typically the most common words in a language. Examples of the most common stop words in the English language are pronouns, articles, prepositions and conjunctions such as a, an, the, and, it, for, or, but, in, my, your, our, and their [7][8]. NLTK has 179 stop words for English language. The first and last 10 stopwords from the NLTK is shown below:

```
stopWordlist = nltk.corpus.stopwords.words("english")
print("number of stop words in nltk: ", len(stopWordlist))

print(stopWordlist[:10])
print(stopWordlist[-10:-1])

number of stop words in nltk: 179
['i', 'me', 'my', 'myself', 'we', 'our', 'ours', 'ourselves', 'you', "you're"]
['shouldn', "shouldn't", 'wasn', "wasn't", 'weren', "weren't", 'won', "won't", 'wouldn']
```

The distribution of words in any human language can be characterized by Zipf's law. The law states: *some terms are more frequent than others* i.e. the most common word will occur approximately twice as often as the second most common word, three times as often as the third most common word, and so on [9]. Stop words, being the most common, adheres Zipf's law, i.e. they are not useful for retrieval of files and hence should be removed.

The bubble plot on Figure-2 below, generated with the *Plotly Express*⁵, for the term frequencies in all 18 files organized in a sorted dictionary (descending order) *before the text pre-processing* step indicates that distribution of terms obeys Zipf's law.

Figure 2 - distribution of terms (tokens) in all files before text pre-processing

⁵ <https://plotly.com/python/plotly-express/>

Removing stop words from the files help to de-noise the texts and improve the performance of retrieval algorithms by focusing on the more relevant words that capture the essence of the document to be retrieved.

A list of stop words for different languages, such as English, German, French, etc., is available from natural language toolkit (NLTK) [8]. An example python code to remove stop words from an English text using nltk is shown below:

```
# select words that are not in the stopword list
def filterStopWords_Text(text_):
    wordlist = nltk.corpus.stopwords.words("english")
    result = []
    for word in text_:
        if not word in wordlist:
            result.append(word)
    return result

# Test text
testText = "This and that can happen at any time of the day"

filterStop_testText = filterStopWords_Text(testText.split())
print("before stopword removal:", testText)
print("after stopword removal:", ' '.join(filterStop_testText))

before stopword removal: This and that can happen at any time of the day
after stopword removal: This happen time day
```

Stemming

Stemming aims to reduce words to their root or base term, known as “stem” [10]. Stemming is particularly useful to for document modeling with inverted index (term-document matrix) (TDM) because it helps to count all variations the stem as a single word.

We can do stemming in python using the *Porter Stemmer algorithm* from the NLTK library [11]. Code below shows the implementation.

```
# stems all words in a file
def stem_Text(text_):
    ps = nltk.stem.PorterStemmer()
    stem = [ps.stem(token) for token in text_]
    return stem

# Test text
testText = "running and runners will run"

# stemming

stem_testText = stem_Text(testText.split())
print("before stemming:", testText)
print("after stemming:", ' '.join(stem_testText))

before stemming: running and runners will run
after stemming: run and runner will run
```

Text cleaning

To build the inverted index structure, which is used to index files based on a query term, all text files must be cleaned using list of functions above. Text cleaning hence means applying case folding, removing special characters, removing stop words, and stemming.

The code snippet below shows text before and after cleaning.

```
def clean_Text(text_):
    text_ = casefold_Text(text_)
    text_ = normalize_Text(text_)
    text_ = filterStopWords_Text(text_)
    text_ = stem_Text(text_)
    return text_

testText = "This is a Test Text that has to be cleaned 155615 [ ] ROBERT ;) DROP TABLE Students;"

clean_text = clean_Text(testText.split())
print("\nbefore cleaning:", testText)
print("after cleaning:", ' '.join(clean_text))

before cleaning: This is a Test Text that has to be cleaned 155615 [ ] ROBERT ;) DROP TABLE Students;
after cleaning: test text clean robert drop tabl student
```

The graph below shows, that even after cleaning the text, still the term distribution in files follows the Zipf's law. The graph indicates a query for files based on common terms such as "shall" would less likely identify one file from another in the information retrieval system.

Figure 3 - distribution of terms after pre-processing step

2.4 Document modeling with Inverted Index (term-document matrix)

One way to model documents is using inverted matrix, also known as term-document matrix (TDM) [12]. The frequency of a term in a file suggests what the document is about. A text file about economics more likely contains jargons related to economics than a text file about chemistry.

To create the matrix, first clean the texts and then identify the list of all unique terms that occur in all files. Finally, for each file assign a number that indicates how many times the term occurs in each file. If the term does not occur in the file, the frequency will be assigned to zero.

Raw term-frequency

The raw term frequency is count of terms in each document without any normalization. The raw frequency of a term (t) in each document (d), is defined as follows [13]:

$$TF_{(t,d)} = \text{count}(t, d) \quad \text{where } TF_{(t,d)} \geq 0$$

The code below shows how to build a term document matrix for a demo text files, file1 and file2.

Figure 4 - Figure shows that the frequency of terms “consumer” and “product” appear in both file 1 & 2 and the rest terms does appear in either of the files.

2.5 Query processing

To retrieve documents, first a user will search files by using a text input much like the way we search in google. Query terms accepted from the user, should then undergo through the same cleaning procedures applied when creating the inverted matrix. This helps to align them with the text representation in the matrix.

Next, score of relevance for each document is calculated by adding how many times a term in the query appears in the term document matrix. This score is normalized in terms of percentage by dividing frequency of query terms in one file to frequency of query terms in all files using a formula:

$$Relevance_{score} = \frac{\sum f_{Qterms_{file}}}{\sum f_{Qterms_{allFiles}}} * 100 \%$$

Finally, the relevance score is stored as a value in a dictionary where the key is name of a file. Further, the dictionary is sorted by value in a descending order, the highest values first.

When retrieving a file, ideally, users are expected to use a combination of key words that are more specific to target files. When a user guesses the right keywords that are more specific to the target file, the search result would most likely be relevant or else the user must try the search again with another key word combinations.

Assume a user is interested to retrieve a file which is about *chemistry* and might search with a query text input of “*chemical product*”. Query processing logic for this scenario, *file1* & *file2*, is shown on the figure below:

Figure 5 - Query processing flow

In the above example, each of the terms “chemical” and “product” are present in the second document one times and only the term “product” is present in the first document only once. Thus, the documents’ relevance score is calculated simply by adding the frequency of terms found in each file and sorting the result to show by order of relevance.

2.6 Query execution results on project Gutenberg files

Figures 4 and 5 use demo files and query to demonstrate the implementation concept in a simplified way. Figures 6, 7 and 8 show bar graphs generated using python's *plotly express*⁶ package for the the execution of query term “*God light heaven*” on the 18 text files used in this project.

Figure 6 – Query result of documents based on raw TDM sorted by relevance score for query input: “*God light heaven*”

The bar graph on Figure 6 above shows, the terms “*God light heaven*” are 71.6% more frequent in the “*bible-kjv*” than the rest of the files. Consequently, searching for “*God light heaven*” results in “*bible-kjv*” being identified as the most relevant document.

2.7 Log-scale Normalization of Inverted Index

Values of raw term frequency is very large when working with large corpus, hence it is necessary to squash it for simplicity. The log scaling is done by taking the log of the raw term frequency and adding a constant number to it to avoid invalid logarithm in cases when the term frequency is zero.

The log scaled term frequency within the inverted index matrix is described as [2]:

$$tf_{t,d} = \begin{cases} 1 + \log_{10} \text{count}(t,d) & \text{if } \text{count}(t,d) > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

⁶ <https://plotly.com/python/plotly-express/>

Log scaling is also beneficial in such cases for downplaying the influence of frequently occurring terms, like "shall" that appear more frequently as shown on Zipf's graph on figure 2. Downplaying frequent terms improves retrieval of the most relevant documents [2].

The effect of penalizing frequently occurring term, leads to a more balanced result for the query as shown on the bar graph on figure-7 below.

Figure 7 – Query result for documents on log scaled TDM sorted by relevance score for query input: “God light heaven”

2.8 Further Normalization with Inverse document frequency

The file retrieval system can be further improved by applying the inverse document frequency (IDF) scaling factor. Applying the IDF helps to emphasize unique terms, terms that are unique to only a specific document (s) [13][14].

The inverse document frequency (IDF) is the ratio of total number of documents (N) to the number of documents on which the document occurs (df_t). When a term occurs only in fewer files, the ratio is higher indicating that the word is unique to specific document(s). For information retrieval systems with large number of files, a log scaling is also applied to the IDF to squash the numbers [13].

The log scaled inverse document frequency (idf_t) [2] is:

$$idf_t = \log_{10} \left(\frac{N}{df_t} \right)$$

The bar graph below shows the search results after log and IDF scaling.

Figure 8 - Query result after log and IDF scaling

3. WebApp implementation with Django

3.1 Data Modeling

To implement the information retrieval WebApp, original text files are stored in the database, without any processing. The inverted index matrix is stored as numpy array at the application layer.

User's search key word requests are accepted via a browser form and then passed to a Django's view function which will perform query processing using the matrix. The query processing returns a dictionary of files and a corresponding sorted score of relevance for each file. Finally, the file names in dictionary are used to index the database to retrieve (open) the files for a view.

When using MongoDB, data modeling is optional to store the files in a schema less fashion. The files are simply stored as a JSON and the dictionary structure is used to get contents of the files from the database. However due to poor compatibility of Django with MongoDB, for this project PostgreSQL database is used for storage of text files in the database.

The data model for storage of text files in postgres is designed so that each file will have three attributes: *title*, *overviews*, and *content*. This model is to help a user-friendly browsing of search results on the user's end. File names are stored on the *title* field, the first 100 characters of the file is stored on the *overview* field and the entire content of the file is stored on *content* field.

Texts corresponding to title, overview and content is extracted from each file and populate the database. The data modeling procedure is shown on the figure below.

Figure 9 - Data modeling steps and the ER model

The data model above is created directly using `models.py` within a Django framework as shown on the [appendix A](#). Python code to populate the files to PostgreSQL as well as MongoDB is shown in [Appendix -1 and 2 respectively](#).

3.2 Django's Model View & template (MVT) implementation steps

After setting up the virtual environment in an empty directory and installing software packages, create a Django project, an application component, and make necessary configuration for paths, templates, database connection, etc.

Import text & query processing functions to `customLibraries.py`, to `views.py`. Then create the user interface with HTML forms that will accept and send user text query to Django application via the view function. Query results from the query processing, within the view function, is then rendered via the HTML to display the result of the query result to the user. The model, view, and template as well as database connection are shown on the figures below.

```
models.py
tdm > models.py > ...
You, 1 second ago | 1 author (You)
1 from django.db import models
2
3 # Model
You, 3 days ago | 1 author (You)
4 class Document(models.Model):
5     docID = models.AutoField(primary_key=True)
6     title = models.CharField(max_length=100, default='Unknown Title')
7     content = models.TextField()
8     overview = models.CharField(max_length=150, default='Unknown Title')
9
10     def __str__(self):
11         return self.title
```

Figure 10- Data modeling with Django

View:

```
views.py
textIirApp > views.py > getQueryText
...
1 from django.shortcuts import render, get_object_or_404
2 from tdm.models import Document
3 from django.views.decorators.csrf import csrf_exempt
4 from django.http import HttpResponseRedirect
5
6
7 from .customLibraries import clean_Text, query_documents, orderByRelevance, renderPlot
8 from .createTDM import tdm, allTerms, tdm_tf, tdm_tfidf
9
10
11 @csrf_exempt
12 def getQueryText(requestIndex):
13
14     if requestIndex.method == 'POST':
15
16         requestDict = requestIndex.POST
17         queryText = str(requestDict["userRequest"])
18         print(queryText)
19
20         # execute the query with tdm
21         # documentScoreArray = query_documents(tdm, allTerms, queryText)
22         # execute the query with tdm_tf
23         # documentScoreArray = query_documents(tdm_tf, allTerms, queryText)
24         documentScoreArray = query_documents(tdm_tf, allTerms, queryText)
25
26         # execute the query with tdm_tfidf
27         # documentScoreArray = query_documents(tdm_tfidf, allTerms, queryText)
28
29         fileNameScore = orderByRelevance(documentScoreArray)
30
31         print(fileNameScore)
32
33         # render plot and Get the image data as a byte string
34         # imgData = renderPlot(fileNameScore, 'blue')
35         # get all document attributes from the database
36         dbDocumentFileIds = Document.objects.all
37
38         return render(requestIndex, 'tdmTemplates/index.html', {'fileNames_scores_': fileNameScore,
39                                                                 'dbDocumentFileIds_': dbDocumentFileIds})
40     else:
41         return render(requestIndex, 'tdmTemplates/index.html')
```

Template:

```
index.html
tdm > templates > tdmTemplates > index.html
121
122
123
124 <!-- INPUT FROM -->
125
126 <div class="formContainer">
127     <form
128         class="input-form"
129         action="{% url 'getQueryText_' %}"
130         method="POST"
131     >
132         {% csrf_token %}
133         <input
134             class="inputfiled"
135             type="text"
136             id="searchInput"
137             name="userRequest"
138             placeholder="query documents ..."
139             style="border-radius: 4px"
140         />
141         <button class="btn-submit" type="submit">Search</button>
142     </form>
143 </div>
144
145 <!-- SEARCH RESULT -->
146
147 <div class="result-container">
148     <table class="table table-hover">
149         <tbody>
150             {% for fileName, score in fileNames_scores.items %}
151             <tr>
152                 <td class="fileScore-column">{{ score }}</td>
153                 <td class="fileName-column">{{ fileName }}</td>
154                 <td class="overview-column">{% if doc.title == fileName %}
155                     <td class="docID-column">
156                         <a href="/tdm/{{ doc.pk }}" class="file-link">{{ doc.pk }}</a>
157                     </td>
158                 {% endif %}
159             </tr>
160             {% endfor %}
161         </tbody>
162     </table>
163 </div>
```

```
settings.py
textIirApp > settings.py > ...
78 DATABASES = {
79     'default': {
80         'ENGINE': 'django.db.backends.postgresql',
81         'NAME': 'ir_test',
82         'USER': 'kopro',
83         'PASSWORD': '1433',
84     }
85 }
86
```

Figure 11 – PostgreSQL database connection in Django

Figure 12 - the information retrieval WebApp UI with a query

Relevance score			document ID in the database
20.7	edgeworth-parents	[The Parent's Assistant, by Maria Edgeworth] THE ORPHANS. (Near the ruins of the castle of Rossmore, in Ireland, is a small cabin, in which there once	33
12.5	bible-kjv	[The King James Bible] The Old Testament of the King James Bible The First Book of Moses: Called Genesis 1:1 In the beginning God created the heaven	25
9.4	whitman-leaves	[Leaves of Grass by Walt Whitman 1855] Come, said my soul, Such verses for my Body let us write, (for we are one,) That should I after return, Or, lo	39
9.3	bryant-stories	[Stories to Tell to Children by Sara Cone Bryant 1918] TWO LITTLE RIDDLES IN RHYME There's a garden that I ken, Full of little gentlemen;	27
9.0	chesterton-brown	[The Wisdom of Father Brown by G. K. Chesterton 1914] I. The Absence of Mr Glass THE consulting-rooms of Dr Orion	31

Figure 13 - Result displayed for the query on the information retrieval WebApp.

4. Ethics concerns

Ethics is a branch of philosophy that focuses on concepts related to right and wrong behavior [15]. File information retrieval systems need to carry significant considerations that extend beyond their technical functionalities. These systems operate within a complex framework that demands careful attention to various ethical and legal aspects. Information retrieval systems must consider factors like privacy, fairness, security, copy right, social impacts, etc.

4.1 Privacy and security

Privacy refers to one's right and ability to keep certain aspects private or share selectively [16]. Protecting user data and maintaining confidentiality is one of major concerns for an information retrieval system. Retrieval systems must adhere to privacy protocols to safeguard sensitive information from unauthorized access or misuse.

Enforcing data privacy in text information retrieval systems involves employing anonymization where personal information is removed from the data, access control where only authorized

individuals will access the data, data minimization where retaining only necessary data required for the retrieval system to minimize risks in case of data breaches, etc.

Robust security measures are must also be implemented for information retrieval systems to prevent breaches, data theft, or system vulnerabilities. Encryption of data, at rest or in transit, and secure authentication protocols are pivotal in safeguarding against potential threats [17].

4.2 Fairness towards Underrepresented Groups

Information retrieval systems must also be fair when representing various social groups. Systems should be designed to avoid biases against certain communities, prevent discrimination in accessing or retrieving files. This involves implementing algorithms that detect and mitigate biases in the data or algorithms to ensure fair and equitable treatment across various social groups [18].

4.3 Copyright

Retrieval systems must also respect intellectual property rights, avoiding unauthorized distribution or usage of copyrighted materials. This involves utilizing algorithms to recognize contents that are copy right protected, meta data tagging to label copyrighted materials to indicate ownership and usage rights, allowing the system to accept takedown requests from copyright owners, implementing algorithms to identify instances where the use of copyrighted material under fair-use exceptions [19].

4.4 Social Impacts

Information retrieval systems shape knowledge dissemination, impact decision-making, and can contribute to shaping public opinion.

The system must acknowledge cultural nuances in content retrieval, respecting diverse cultural perspectives, languages, and values to prevent conflicts. Furthermore, information retrieval systems must uphold ethical standards in content distribution, avoid propagation of misleading, false, or harmful information [20].

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Appendix – A: Django’s Model and View

```
# Model
from django.db import models
class Document(models.Model):
    docID = models.AutoField(primary_key=True)
    title = models.CharField(max_length=100, default='Unknown Title')
    content = models.TextField()
    overview = models.CharField(max_length=150, default='Unknown Title')

    def __str__(self):
        return self.title

# views
from django.shortcuts import render, get_object_or_404
from .models import Document

def queryResults(requestDocs):

    # get all documents in the databse
    documents = Document.objects.all

    # render results to the html page
    return render(requestDocs,
                  'tdmTempltes/filesInDB.html',
                  {'documents_': documents})

def getDocumentDetails_tdm(requestDetails, pkkk):

    # 'docID' is a primary key field in the Documents
    # docID=pkkk will assign the primary key to the pkkk argument

    docDetails_tdm = get_object_or_404(Document, pk=pkkk)
    return render(requestDetails,
                  'tdmTempltes/documentDetails.html',
                  {'docDetails_tdm_': docDetails_tdm})
```

Appendix – B: Inserting text to the DB

```
import psycopg2
from .getContents import getDocTitles, getOverviews, getContents

# setup db connection
conn = psycopg2.connect(
    dbname="irDB",
    user="kobro",
    password="1433",
    host="localhost",
    port="5432"
)

# get file names

fileDir_ = 'gutenberg'

titles = getDocTitles()
overviews = getOverviews(fileDir_)
contents = getContents(fileDir_)

# Create a cursor object using the connection
cur = conn.cursor()

# SQL statement for data insertion into table 'tdm_documents '
sql = "INSERT INTO tdm_document (title, overview, content) VALUES (%s,
%s, %s)"

# Execute the SQL statement for each tuple in the list
for title, overview, content in zip(titles, overviews, contents):
    data = (title, overview, content)
    cur.execute(sql, data)

# Commit the transaction and close the cursor and connection
conn.commit()
cur.close()
conn.close()
```

Appendix – C: Text per-processing functions

```
import re
import nltk
import collections
import numpy as np

def load_allfiles():
    # load all files from gutenber
    file_names = nltk.corpus.gutenberg.fileids()
    return [nltk.corpus.gutenberg.words(file) for file in file_names]

# clean text
def clean_Text(tokenList_):

    tokenList_ = casefold_Text(tokenList_)
    tokenList_ = normalize_Text(tokenList_)
    tokenList_ = filterStopWords_Text(tokenList_)
    tokenList_ = stem_Text(tokenList_)
    return tokenList_

# case folding
def casefold_Text(tokenList_):
    return [word.casefold() for word in tokenList_]

# cleaning special characters
def normalize_Text(tokenList_):
    pattern = r"^[a-zA-Z0-9]"
    clean_tokens = [re.sub(pattern, '', token) for token in tokenList_]
    clean_tokens = list(filter(None, clean_tokens))
    return clean_tokens

# select words that are not in the stopword list
def filterStopWords_Text(tokenList_):

    wordlist = nltk.corpus.stopwords.words("english")
    result = []
    for word in tokenList_:
        if not word in wordlist:
            result.append(word)
    return result

# stems all words in a file
def stem_Text(tokenList_):
    ps = nltk.stem.PorterStemmer()
    return [ps.stem(token) for token in tokenList_]
```

```
# clean all files in one go
def clean_Files(files_):

    files_ = casefold_Files(files_)
    files_ = normalize_Files(files_)
    files_ = remove_stopwords_Files(files_)
    cleanCorpus = stem_Files(files_)

    return cleanCorpus

# casefold all files
def casefold_Files(files_):
    return [casefold_Text(file) for file in files_]

# remove special characters
def normalize_Files(files_):
    return [normalize_Text(file) for file in files_]

# remove stop words
def remove_stopwords_Files(files_):
    return [filterStopWords_Text(file) for file in files_]

# stems all words in a file
def stem_Files(files_):
    return [stem_Text(file) for file in files_]
```

Appendix – D: Inverted Matrix

```
def create_term_document_matrix(all_files_):
    # get the summary of the corpus
    counter_corpus, counter_documents = summarize_Files(all_files_)

    # create an empty matrix with the correct dimension
    tdm = np.zeros((len(counter_corpus), len(all_files_)))

    for idx, word in enumerate(counter_corpus):
        for document_id in range(len(all_files_)):
            if word in counter_documents[document_id]:
                tdm[idx,document_id]= counter_documents[document_id][word]
    return (tdm, list(counter_corpus.keys()))

# count all unique tokens in all files
def summarize_Files(files_):
    counters = [collections.Counter(file) for file in files_]

    # create empty counter
    counter_tmp = collections.Counter()
    # iterate counter and sum up
    for c in counters:
        counter_tmp += c
    return (counter_tmp, counters)
```

Appendix – E: Query processing and optimization

```
def query_documents(tdm, terms, queryText_, idf_):
    # if idf_ is True, apply idf scaling
    if idf_:
        tdm = scale_tfidf(tdm)

    # change query text into tokens
    queryText_ = queryText_.split()

    # clean the tokens
    queryText_clean = clean_Text(queryText_)

    # build score
    idxs = [terms.index(word) for word in queryText_clean if word in terms]
    documentScore = tdm[idxs].sum(axis=0)
    return documentScore

def logScale_tf(tdm):
    return np.log1p(tdm+1)
```

```

def scale_tfidf(tdm_):
    tdm_ = logScale_tf(tdm_)
    tmp = tdm_ != 0
    num_documents = tdm_.shape[1]
    idf = np.log(num_documents/tdm_.sum(axis=1))
    return (tdm_.T * idf).T

```

Appendix – E: Results in order of relevance

```

# present data by order of relevance
def mapFilesToScore(docScore):
    file_names = [title.split('.')[0]
                  for title in nltk.corpus.gutenberg.fileids()]
    fileName_score_ = {}
    for file, score in zip(file_names, docScore):
        fileName_score_[file] = score
    return fileName_score_

def orderByRelevance(docScore):

    docScore = (docScore / np.sum(docScore)) * 100. # normalize scores
    docScore = list(np.round(docScore, 1))          # rounding
    fileName_score_map = mapFilesToScore(docScore) # map file names to score

    # sort results in descending order
    fileName_score_Sorted = dict(
        sorted(fileName_score_map.items(),
              key=lambda item: item[1], reverse=True))

    #Filter values greater than 0
    fileName_score_Sorted = {key: value for key,
                             value in fileName_score_Sorted.items() if value > 0}
    return fileName_score_Sorted

```

Appendix – F: Generate plots

```
def barPlot(dict_,
            color_='green',
            title_='Query result of relevant documents'):

    import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
    plt.style.use('bmh')
    labels = list(dict_.keys())
    values = list(dict_.values())
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 6))
    ax.bar(labels, values, color=color_)
    ax.xlabel('file names')
    ax.ylabel('Percentage of document\'s relevance')
    ax.title(title_)
    ax.xticks(rotation=90) # Rotate x-axis labels for better visibility
    return fig

plt.close(plot_)
```